

Supplementary material for “Assessing HRTF preprocessing methods for
Ambisonics rendering through perceptual models”
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Table 1: Mean absolute ITD error between each method and the reference, per order (in microseconds).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	44
Trunc	296	231.4	169.3	100.9	40.9	12.6	9.3	14.5	5	5.2	1.6	0.8	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.1
EQ	319	254.9	189.5	111.6	43.3	12.8	9.7	14.5	5.2	4.9	1.6	0.8	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.1
Tap	332.5	259.5	223.6	149.4	59.1	13.6	9.6	14.6	5.2	5	1.6	0.8	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.1
TA	58.1	34.5	30	19.9	12.6	7.3	5.8	6.4	4.9	3	1.1	0.5	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1
MagLS	404.5	410.9	290.6	143.5	47.7	12.7	9.2	14.4	5.3	4.9	1.6	0.8	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.1
MagLS+CC	340	388.9	295.4	149.7	49.3	13.6	8.8	14.5	5.2	5	1.6	0.8	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.1
SpSub	241.2	192.4	156.6	93.9	42.3	13.4	13.6	12.1	6.9	4.8	1.6	1.1	0.4	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.3
SpSubMod	412.2	363.3	297.8	117.8	33	11.5	13.4	12.2	6.9	4.5	1.6	1.1	0.4	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3
BiMagLS	56.7	31.6	29.7	20.2	11.8	7.3	5.4	6.4	4.9	2.8	1.3	0.5	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1

Table 2: Mean absolute ILD error between each method and the reference, per order (in dB).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	44
Trunc	4.8	3.3	2.9	2.5	2.3	2.1	1.9	1.7	1.5	1.3	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1
EQ	4.8	3.3	2.9	2.5	2.3	2.1	1.9	1.7	1.5	1.3	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1
Tap	4.1	2.6	1.7	1.6	2.8	2.6	2.3	2	1.9	1.7	1.4	0.6	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
TA	1.8	1.4	1.1	0.9	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0
MagLS	1.7	1.1	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1
MagLS+CC	2.9	1.6	1.1	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1
SpSub	4.6	3.9	3.2	2.8	2.8	2.3	2	1.8	1.7	1.3	1	0.8	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1
SpSubMod	2.3	1.7	1.2	1	0.9	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1
BiMagLS	1.2	1	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0

Table 3: Average PSD between each method and the reference, per order (in sones).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	44
Trunc	1.45	1.3	1.16	1.03	0.91	0.8	0.72	0.66	0.61	0.56	0.37	0.22	0.12	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.04
EQ	0.97	0.92	0.87	0.82	0.74	0.67	0.61	0.57	0.53	0.49	0.34	0.2	0.12	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.04
Tap	0.91	0.9	0.86	0.81	0.79	0.72	0.65	0.6	0.56	0.53	0.4	0.24	0.13	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.04
TA	0.65	0.48	0.38	0.3	0.26	0.22	0.19	0.17	0.15	0.14	0.1	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04
MagLS	0.5	0.36	0.27	0.24	0.21	0.21	0.19	0.18	0.16	0.15	0.11	0.1	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.04
MagLS+CC	0.65	0.45	0.31	0.25	0.22	0.21	0.2	0.18	0.16	0.15	0.11	0.1	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.04
SpSub	1	0.8	0.79	0.69	0.68	0.55	0.51	0.44	0.39	0.36	0.28	0.19	0.12	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.05
SpSubMod	0.78	0.54	0.43	0.35	0.31	0.26	0.24	0.22	0.19	0.19	0.13	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.05
BiMagLS	0.52	0.35	0.27	0.22	0.19	0.16	0.15	0.13	0.12	0.11	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04

Table 4: Lateral precision per method and order (in degrees). Reference: 3°.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	44
Trunc	30.2	23.7	17.9	11.9	8.4	7.1	6.8	6.5	6.1	5.9	4.4	3.5	3.2	3.2	3.1	3.1	3.1
EQ	30.1	23.7	17.8	11.9	8.4	7.1	6.9	6.5	6.1	5.8	4.4	3.6	3.2	3.1	3.1	3	3.1
Tap	29.1	22.6	15.5	10.3	5.9	5.6	5.3	5	5.2	5.1	4.4	3.5	3.2	3.2	3.1	3	3.1
TA	8.7	7.2	6	5.3	5	4.8	4.5	4.3	3.9	4.1	3.5	3.1	3.1	3.1	3.1	3	3
MagLS	32.4	28.8	16.8	9	4.7	4.1	4.3	4.3	4.7	4.8	4.1	3.5	3.2	3.2	3.1	3	3.1
MagLS+CC	28.4	30.1	17.3	9.1	4.7	4.2	4.3	4.2	4.6	4.8	4.1	3.5	3.2	3.1	3	3.1	3.1
SpSub	29.4	21.6	19	11.8	9.4	7.3	7.3	6.5	6.5	5.8	4.3	3.7	3.3	3.2	3.1	3	3.1
SpSubMod	33	31.5	20.8	9.1	5.1	4.4	4.5	4.4	4.4	4.2	3.9	3.6	3.3	3.2	3.1	3.1	3.1
BiMagLS	7.5	6.4	5.5	4.5	4.2	4	3.9	3.7	3.5	3.5	3.4	3.2	3.1	3	3.1	3	3

Table 5: Polar precision per method and order (in degrees). Reference: 16.39°.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	44
Trunc	78.6	78.7	76.2	73.8	72.9	69.2	64.9	58.6	51	48.4	27.7	18.8	19	18.2	17.3	16.7	17
EQ	78.8	78.7	75.9	73.4	72.6	69.3	64.9	58.1	50.6	48.4	27	20	19.1	18.9	16.9	17.3	17.2
Tap	78.8	78.5	75.7	68.2	65.2	61.8	59.4	54.6	48.8	46.9	28.8	19.3	19.1	18.9	17.8	16.9	17.3
TA	63.6	51.4	42	33.5	27.4	25.8	21.8	21.4	20.1	19.8	17.4	18.5	18	17.4	17.8	17.2	17.8
MagLS	64.1	58.4	43.9	28.6	23.4	22.8	25.1	25.5	24.8	26.4	22.5	19.2	18.8	18.7	17.8	17.5	16.9
MagLS+CC	70.6	59.9	43.1	28.9	23.9	24.5	25	24.4	25.1	26	22.1	19.2	19.2	18.5	17.4	17.2	17.9
SpSub	79.8	62	63.2	62.3	63.4	59.1	54.8	51.7	47.6	43.5	26.9	20.1	18.4	18.1	17.7	17.7	17
SpSubMod	66.1	64	52.5	43.6	30.8	26.6	22.9	23.2	22.7	24.3	22.6	19.3	19	18.1	17.5	18.1	17
BiMagLS	51.7	36.2	30.4	24.4	21.8	21	19.9	20.1	19.1	18.4	18.1	18	18.2	18.1	17.3	16.7	17.4

Table 6: Externalisation per method and order. Reference: 1.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	44
Trunc	0.46	0.5	0.45	0.54	0.55	0.58	0.62	0.59	0.64	0.68	0.81	0.89	0.95	0.98	0.99	1	1
EQ	0.46	0.5	0.45	0.54	0.55	0.58	0.62	0.59	0.64	0.68	0.81	0.89	0.95	0.98	0.99	1	1
Tap	0.5	0.46	0.56	0.51	0.53	0.54	0.63	0.66	0.64	0.72	0.79	0.91	0.95	0.98	0.99	1	1
TA	0.73	0.77	0.83	0.88	0.91	0.94	0.95	0.96	0.97	0.96	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	1	1
MagLS	0.83	0.85	0.92	0.93	0.95	0.96	0.96	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.98	0.99	0.99	1	1
MagLS+CC	0.82	0.85	0.91	0.94	0.95	0.96	0.95	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.96	0.98	0.99	0.99	1	1
SpSub	0.4	0.58	0.53	0.62	0.62	0.63	0.66	0.7	0.74	0.79	0.85	0.9	0.95	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99
SpSubMod	0.65	0.73	0.83	0.85	0.88	0.92	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.93	0.96	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99
BiMagLS	0.83	0.86	0.91	0.93	0.95	0.96	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	1	1

Table 7: Spatial release from masking per method and order (in dB). Reference: 8.6 dB.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	44
Trunc	3.7	4.6	5.2	5.7	6.3	7.2	7.6	7.8	7.9	8	8.5	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6
EQ	3.7	4.6	5.2	5.7	6.3	7.1	7.6	7.8	7.9	8	8.5	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6
Tap	5.1	4.8	7	6.8	8	8.4	8.4	8.3	8.3	8.3	8.5	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6
TA	9	9	8.7	8.5	8.7	8.8	8.8	8.6	8.7	8.7	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6
MagLS	7.3	8.1	7.7	7.6	7.9	8.1	8.2	8.2	8.1	8.2	8.5	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6
MagLS+CC	6.2	7.2	7.3	7.6	7.9	8	8.2	8.2	8.1	8.2	8.5	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6
SpSub	4.8	7.2	6.6	6.8	7	7.5	7.7	7.9	8	8	8.5	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6
SpSubMod	6.8	8.3	8.3	8.2	8.4	8.3	8.5	8.4	8.3	8.3	8.5	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6
BiMagLS	9.2	8.9	8.7	8.3	8.4	8.7	8.7	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.6	8.5	8.6	8.6	8.6